

pH metric investigation on chemical speciation of Co^{II}, Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} complexes with 5-hydroxysalicylic acid in urea-water mixtures

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Abstract : Chemical speciation of binary complexes of Co^{II}, Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} ions with 5-hydroxysalicylic acid (5-HSA) in the concentration range of 5.8–42.47% w/v urea-water mixtures at an ionic strength of 0.16 mol dm⁻³ and temperature 303 K were investigated pH metrically. The existence and stability of different binary complex species and also the effect of urea on the speciation have been established by using the computer program MINIQUAD75. The species detected are ML₂H₂, ML₂H₃ and ML₂H₄ for Co^{II}, Ni^{II} and Cu^{II}. The linear variation of stability constants of the complexes with increasing urea was explained by electrostatic forces.

Keywords : 5-Hydroxysalicylic acid, speciation, urea-water, binary complexes, dielectric constant.

Introduction

The toxicity, bioavailability, bioaccumulation, biodegradability, persistence, mobility, solubility, extractability and many other critical properties depend on the form and nature of the chemical species^{1,2}. Bioavailability of metal ions depends on either in free state or in binding state or in complexation state with various constituents present in the requisite amounts during biological reactions. The changes in various constraints like change in pH, temperature, ionic strength cause change in complexation behaviour of metals and binding state. So complexation can signify the bioavailability of the metal ions in various biosystems^{3,4}. Speciation analysis, the determination of the concentrations of separate and unique atomic and molecular forms of an element instead of its total concentration in a sample is important in human biology, nutrition, toxicology and in clinical practice⁵. The

speciation study of toxic and essential metal ion complexes is also useful to understand the role played by the active site cavities in biological molecules.

Speciation analysis, the determination of the concentrations of separate and unique atomic and molecular forms of an element instead of its total concentration in a sample is important in human biology, nutrition, toxicology and in clinical practice⁶⁻⁸. On the other hand, speciation profoundly influences both the toxicity and bioavailability of an element. Cobalt is essential for the production of red blood cells. It acts as coenzyme in several biochemical processes. Cobalt in the form of vitamin B12 is essential for animals. Vitamin B12 is synthesized only by microorganisms, in particular anaerobic bacteria. Nickel is associated with several enzymes⁹⁻¹¹ and any variation in its concentration leads to metabolic disorders. Copper is largely rejected from cells but outside the cell, it is essential

for the metabolism of many hormones and connective tissue. The biological functions include electron transfer, dioxygen transport, oxygenation, oxidation, reduction and disproportionate^{12,13}.

The aim of the present study is to understand the role of metal ions at active site cavities in bioactive molecules like drugs, enzymes and proteins to know the effect of dielectric constant of the medium on the chemical speciation of the title systems. 5-HSA has been taken as a model compound for drug residues, since the dielectric constant at the active site cavities is very small compared to that at bio-fluids, and low dielectric constant is mimicked by using a water soluble organic solvent like urea.

For equilibria in solution, usually the equilibrium constants are measured for the individual reactions and the species concentrations are calculated by solving the mass-balance equations. This approach was pioneered in the programs HALTAFALL¹⁴ and COMICS¹⁵, which were written to solve sets of equations that typically might arise with systems of one or two metal ions and one or two ligands. Since the development of these programs and with advances in computer speed and availability, a number of computer programs for the simulation of metal-ligand equilibria in aqueous systems have been developed. These include ECCLES¹⁶, MINEQL¹⁷, SCOGS¹⁸, SOLMNQ¹⁹, COMLOT²⁰, SPE²¹, ESTA²², GEOCHEM²³, JESS²⁴, visual MINTEQ²⁵, CHEAQS²⁶ and HYSS²⁷. They are static models which calculate the chemical equilibrium distribution of aqueous species in a solution and in some cases, the saturation indices for solid phases. Other programs such as PHREEQC²⁸ and EQ3/6²⁹ perform the same function as the chemical speciation models but, in addition, they may be used as dynamic models capable of predicting the path of a reacting system.

Experimental

Chemicals :

5-HSA (TCI, India) solution (0.05 mol L⁻¹) was prepared in triple-distilled deionised water by maintaining 0.05 mol L⁻¹ hydrochloric acid concentration

to increase the solubility. Urea (Qualigens, India) was used as received. 2 mol L⁻¹ sodium chloride (Qualigens, India) solution was prepared to maintain the ionic strength in the titrand. 0.1 mol L⁻¹ aqueous solutions of Co^{II}, Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} chlorides were prepared by dissolving G.R. grade (E. Merck, India) salts in triple-distilled water by maintaining 0.05 mol L⁻¹ hydrochloric acid to suppress the hydrolysis of metal salts. All the solutions were standardized by standard methods. To assess the errors that might have crept into the determination of the concentrations, the data were subjected to analysis of variance of one way classification^{30,31}. The strengths of alkali and mineral acid were determined using the Gran plot method^{32,33}.

Equipment :

The titrimetric data were obtained using EQUIPTRONICS (Model EQ 614 A) pH meter (readability 0.01), which was calibrated with 0.05 mol L⁻¹ potassium hydrogen phthalate in acidic region and 0.01 mol L⁻¹ borax solution in basic region. The glass electrode was equilibrated in a well stirred urea-water mixture containing the inert electrolyte. All the titrations were carried out in the medium containing varying concentrations of urea-water mixtures (0.0–42.47% w/v) by maintaining an ionic strength of 0.16 mol L⁻¹ using sodium chloride at 303.0±0.1 K. The effect of variation in asymmetry potential, liquid junction potential, activity coefficient, sodium ion error and dissolved carbon dioxide on the response of glass electrode was accounted for in the form of correction factor³⁴.

Procedure :

For the determination of stability constants of metal-ligand binary species, initially titrations of strong acid with alkali were carried out at regular intervals to check whether complete equilibration was achieved. In each of the titrations, the titrand consisted of approximately 1 mmol mineral acid in a total volume of 50 mL. Titrations with different ratios (1 : 2.5, 1 : 3.75 and 1 : 5.0) of metal-to-ligand were carried out using 0.4 mol L⁻¹ of sodium hydroxide. Other experimental details are given elsewhere^{35,36}.

Modeling strategy :

The computer program SCPHD^{37,38} was used to calculate the correction factor. By using the pH-metric titration data, the binary stability constants were calculated with the computer program MINQUAD75^{39,40}, which exploit the advantage of the constrained least-squares method in the initial refinement and reliable convergence of Marquardt algorithm. During the refinement of binary systems, the correction factor and the protonation constants of 5-HSA were fixed. The variation of stability constants with the dielectric constant of the medium was analyzed on electrostatic grounds on the basis of solute-solute and solute-solvent interactions.

Results and discussion

The results of the final best-fit models that contain the stoichiometry of the complex species and their overall formation constants along with some of the important statistical parameters are given in Table 1. Very low-standard deviation in overall stability constants ($\log \beta$) signifies the precision of these constants. The small values of U_{corr} (sum of squares of deviations in concentrations of ingredients at all experimental points) corrected for degrees of freedom, small values of mean, standard deviation and mean deviation for the systems are validated by the residual analysis^{41,42}.

Residual analysis :

The results of the best-fit models that contain the type of species and overall formation constants along with some of the important statistical parameters are given in Table 1. A very low standard deviation in $\log \beta$ values indicates the precision of these parameters. Small values of U_{corr} (sum of squares of deviations in concentrations of ingredients at all experimental points corrected for degrees of freedom) indicate that the experimental data can be represented by the models. Small values of mean, standard deviation and mean deviation for the systems corroborate that the residuals are around a zero mean with little dispersion. For an ideal normal distribution, the values of Kurtosis

and Skewness should be three and zero, respectively. Kurtosis is a measure of the peakedness of the error distribution near a modal value. For an ideal normal distribution Kurtosis value should be three (mesokurtic). If the Kurtosis is less than three, the peak of the error distribution curve is flat (platykurtic) and if the Kurtosis is greater than three, the distribution shall have sharp peak (leptokurtic). The Kurtosis values in the present study indicate that the residuals form leptokurtic as well as platykurtic patterns for Co^{II}, Ni^{II} and Cu^{II}. The values of Skewness recorded in Table 1 are between -0.06 and 1.83 for Co^{II}, -0.09 and 1.53 for Ni^{II}, -0.11 and 0.23 for Cu^{II}. These data evince that the residuals form part of a normal distribution. Hence, the least-squares method can be applied to the present data. The sufficiency of the model is further evident from the low crystallographic R -value recorded. These statistical parameters thus show that the best-fit models portray the metal-ligand species in urea-water mixtures.

In data analysis with least squares methods, the residuals (the differences between the experimental data and the data simulated based on model parameters) are assumed to follow Gaussian or normal distribution. When the data are fit into the models, the residuals should ideally be equal to zero. If statistical measures of the residuals and the errors assumed in the models are not significantly different from each other, the model is said to be adequate. Further, a model is considered adequate only if the residuals do not show any trend. Respecting the hypothesis that the errors are random, the residuals are tested for normal distribution. Such tests are χ^2 , Skewness, Kurtosis and R -factor⁴³. These statistical parameters show that the best-fit models portray the metal-ligand species in urea-water mixtures, as discussed below.

Effect of systematic errors on best-fit model :

In order to rely upon the best-fit chemical model for critical evaluation and application under varied experimental conditions with different accuracies of data acquisition, an investigation was undertaken by introducing pessimistic errors in the influential param-

Table 1. Parameters of best fit chemical models of Co^{II}, Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} – 5-HSA complexes in urea-water mixtures
Temp. = 303 K, ionic strength = 0.16 mol dm⁻³

% w/v Urea	log β_{mlh} (SD)			pH- range	NP	U_{corr}	χ^2	Skewness	Kurtosis	<i>R</i> -factor
	ML ₂ H ₂	ML ₂ H ₃	ML ₂ H ₄							
				Co ^{II}						
0.0	27.67(12)	35.40(37)	37.51(40)	2.0–11.5	101	28.26	9.58	-0.06	2.75	0.03518
5.8	27.42(18)	34.84(50)	36.94(64)	2.3–11.3	71	61.47	19.53	1.03	5.69	0.07862
11.52	27.18(21)	34.44(42)	36.52(60)	2.6–10.9	38	17.91	37.96	1.83	6.41	0.03889
20.31	26.94(37)	34.07(77)	36.27(37)	2.8–10.9	61	60.86	10.44	0.60	4.83	0.06772
29.64	26.41(32)	33.85(56)	36.15(86)	2.9–10.9	63	97.33	49.74	1.61	6.89	0.08804
36.83	26.11(23)	33.58(41)	36.62(53)	3.3–10.9	42	254.1	12.16	0.36	4.30	0.04487
42.47	25.89(66)	33.12(65)	37.10(73)	4.3–10.6	18	14.06	4.96	0.02	2.82	0.03121
				Ni ^{II}						
0.0	27.31(09)	34.88(36)	36.79(40)	2.0–11.5	102	24.24	8.88	-0.09	3.09	0.03369
5.8	27.50(16)	34.51(34)	36.98(25)	2.8–11.4	68	37.23	31.14	0.44	4.29	0.05040
11.52	27.14(29)	34.26(49)	37.32(83)	3.0–11.2	21	15.61	12.30	0.47	4.16	0.02701
20.31	26.88(21)	33.89(41)	37.80(60)	2.9–10.9	42	48.97	52.10	1.53	5.39	0.04664
29.64	26.42(20)	33.48(47)	38.11(59)	3.0–11.1	39	26.33	40.61	0.53	5.91	0.04474
36.83	26.64(20)	33.15(48)	37.81(69)	3.0–11.1	42	28.97	4.03	0.67	3.26	0.04027
42.47	27.01(32)	32.86(48)	38.00(67)	3.5–11.1	32	18.75	6.50	0.47	2.93	0.03439
				Cu ^{II}						
0.0	26.32(13)	31.87(37)	34.98(40)	2.0–11.5	99	34.16	15.65	-0.11	4.61	0.03952
5.8	25.93(30)	32.45(61)	35.56(63)	2.8–11.0	56	53.20	10.57	0.23	3.76	0.05861
11.52	26.53(13)	32.83(43)	36.31(72)	3.2–11.5	49	29.13	13.93	0.61	3.92	0.45046
20.31	26.84(12)	33.22(41)	36.79(56)	3.6–11.5	42	23.05	24.10	0.20	5.63	0.04383
29.64	26.97(27)	33.63(02)	36.97(54)	3.7–11.8	61	23.12	37.57	-0.03	4.35	0.09132
36.83	27.22(40)	33.84(51)	37.30(45)	4.2–10.6	29	22.92	10.38	0.03	3.78	0.04322
42.47	27.48(36)	34.05(44)	37.88(46)	4.4–10.6	27	14.41	6.01	0.10	3.76	0.03378

$U_{corr} = U/(NP - m)$; m = number of species; NP = number of experimental points; SD = standard deviation.

eters like concentrations of alkali, mineral acid, ligand, metal, log F and volume in Table 2. The order of the ingredients that influence the magnitudes of stability constants due to incorporation of errors is alkali > acid > metal > ligand > volume > log F . Some species were even rejected when errors were introduced in the concentrations. The rejection of some species and increased standard deviations in the stability constants on introduction of errors confirm the suitability of the experimental conditions (concentrations of ingredients) and choice of the best-fit models.

Effect of solvent :

The dielectric constant is one of the characteristics of liquid. The metal-ligand stability constants are strongly affected by the dielectric constant of the medium because of the fact that at least one of the con-

stituents is charged and other is either changed or has a dipole.

When the ionization of an acid gives a net increase of ions, a decrease in the dielectric constant of the solvent should be accompanied by an increase in the stability constant of a weak acid dissolved in it. The variation of stability constant or change in free energy with co-solvent content depends upon two factors, viz. electrostatic and non-electrostatic forces. Born's classical treatment holds good in accounting for the electrostatic contribution to the free energy change⁴⁴. According to this treatment, the energy of electrostatic interaction or stability constants should vary linearly as a function of the reciprocal of the dielectric constant ($1/D$) of the medium. Such linear variation of stability constants of 5-HSA in urea-water mixtures

Table 2. Effect of errors in influential parameters on Cu^{II} and 5-HSA complex stability constants in 5.8% w/v urea-water mixture

Ingredient	% Error	log β_{mlh} (SD)		
		122	123	124
Acid	0	25.93(30)	32.45(61)	35.56(63)
	-5	Rejected	28.37(154)	32.06(53)
	-3	Rejected	29.47(85)	35.56(63)
	+3	26.91(37)	33.67(61)	33.17(58)
	+5	27.61(71)	35.10(83)	40.36(105)
Alkali	-5	Rejected	32.14(91)	37.10(102)
	-3	27.25(80)	33.46(81)	36.75(93)
	+3	24.88(101)	35.20(97)	38.21(63)
	+5	24.12(45)	Rejected	Rejected
	Ligand	-5	26.30(49)	32.11(84)
Metal	-3	25.26(88)	31.51(71)	36.15(92)
	+3	24.68(89)	33.23(121)	34.27(98)
	+5	26.81(87)	32.28(58)	36.74(89)
	-5	24.98(92)	32.06(95)	36.28(85)
	-3	26.12(98)	33.21(101)	36.66(56)
Volume	+3	25.01(68)	30.25(91)	34.12(93)
	+5	25.56(80)	31.65(111)	35.21(39)
	-5	26.11(45)	32.42(75)	36.01(58)
	-3	26.84(52)	32.65(69)	34.21(82)
	+3	25.19(61)	31.89(46)	33.23(33)
log F	+5	26.58(32)	32.46(55)	37.10(117)
	-5	26.10(90)	31.99(41)	36.68(43)
	-3	26.21(89)	30.65(76)	35.45(58)
	+3	25.88(27)	31.85(63)	35.62(33)
	+5	25.25(80)	32.67(83)	34.25(87)

shows the dominance of electrostatic interactions and the trend is shown in Fig. 1.

A plot of log β versus $1/D$ (D is dielectric constant) should be linear if Born's classical treatment holds good indicating that electrostatic forces alone operate. The values of Co^{II}, Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} complexes of 5-HSA with $1/D$ reveals that the electrostatic forces are dominating the equilibrium process under the present experimental conditions. The solute-solvent interactions, relative thermodynamic stabilities and kinetic liabilities are also expected to play an important role.

Distribution diagrams :

5-HSA is a tridentate ligand, it has one carboxyl (-COOH), two hydroxyl (-OH) groups. The different forms of 5-HSA are LH₃, LH₂⁻, and LH₂²⁻ in the pH

Fig. 1. Variation of overall stability constant values of metal-5-HSA complexes with $1/D$ of urea-water mixtures : (a) Co^{II}, (b) Ni^{II}, (c) Cu^{II}; (■) log $\beta_{ML_2H_2}$, (●) log $\beta_{ML_2H_3}$, (▲) log $\beta_{ML_2H_4}$.

range 1.5–6.5, 1.5–11.5, and 5.5–11.5, respectively. Hence, the plausible binary metal-ligand complexes can be predicted from these data. The present investigation reveals the existence of ML_2H_2 , ML_2H_3 and ML_2H_4 for Co^{II} , Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} .

The formation of various 5-HSA complex species is shown in the following equilibria.

Some typical distribution diagrams in urea-water mixtures are shown in Fig. 2. They indicate that the binary complexes of Co^{II} , Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} are formed in the pH range 1.6–11.5. ML_2H_4 species are formed at

Fig. 2. Distribution diagrams of binary complexes of 5-HSA in 29.64% w/v urea-water mixture : (a) Co^{II} , (b) Ni^{II} and (c) Cu^{II} .

pH 1.6 and deprotonated by increasing pH (Equilibrium 11). ML₂H₃ and ML₂H₂ are simultaneously formed with the increasing pH (Equilibrium 12 and 13). ML₂H₃ and ML₂H₂ species percentage successively increases with increasing pH. ML₂H₃ species were formed in the pH range 1.5–10.0 with highest percentage of species at pH 4.0. ML₂H₂ species were formed in the pH range 4.0–11.5 with highest percentage of species at pH 10.0 for Co^{II} and Ni^{II} respectively. For Cu^{II}, ML₂H₃ species were formed in the pH range 1.5–8.0 with highest percentage of species

at pH 4.0. ML₂H₂ species were formed in the pH range 2.5–11.5 with highest percentage of species at pH 9.5.

Structures of complexes :

5-HSA has three functional groups such as one -COOH and two -OH groups, and is helpful to form different complexes with Co^{II}, Ni^{II} and Cu^{II}. Octahedral structures are proposed to the complexes of all the metal ions. The VSEPR theory suggests that Co^{II}, Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} complexes shall be octahedral because, there are six outer electron pairs. This argument supports the structures of complexes proposed in Fig. 3.

Conclusions

The following conclusions have been drawn from the modeling studies of 5-HSA complexes of Co^{II}, Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} in urea-water mixtures.

- (i) 5-HSA forms both protonated and unprotonated complexes under pH range 1.5–11.5.
- (ii) The complex species formed due to interaction of 5-HSA with the essential metals are ML₂H₂, ML₂H₃ and ML₂H₄.
- (iii) The linear variation of the stability constants with 1/*D* of the urea indicates the dominance of electrostatic forces over non-electrostatic forces.
- (iv) The order of the components in influencing the magnitudes of the stability constants due to incorporation of errors is alkali > acid > ligand > metal > volume > log *F*.
- (v) Some species are stabilized due to electrostatic interactions and some are destabilized due to the decreased dielectric constant.

Fig. 3. Structure of 5-HSA complexes, where S is either solvent or water molecules.

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